

THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL VALUES, JOB SATISFACTION, ORGANIZATIONAL SILENCE AND AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT

Zülfü Demirtaş¹

Fırat University,
Faculty of Education,
Turkey

Abstract:

In this research, the relationships between organizational values, job satisfaction, organizational silence and affective commitment perceptions of managers and teachers working in schools were examined. The research data were collected from 706 school administrators and teachers. Four scales were used in the study: Management Scale According to Values, Teaching Satisfaction Scale, Organizational Silence Scale and Affective Commitment Scale. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was developed to determine the relationship between variables. The data obtained in the SEM show that all hypotheses of the study are accepted. According to these findings, organizational values positively affect job satisfaction and affective commitment. Organizational values have a negative effect on organizational silence. Job satisfaction has a positive effect affective commitment. Organizational silence negatively affects affective commitment. Job satisfaction increases the influence of organizational values on affective commitment with the role of mediator. Organizational silence diminishes the role of the mediator and the influence of organizational values on affective commitment.

Keywords: organizational values, job satisfaction, organizational silence, affective commitment, structural equation modeling

1. Introduction

The reason for the existence of schools is to meet the educational needs of the society. The schools that emerged for this purpose can be defined as service organizations that provide teaching services to the students. In order to exist, all organizations need the common objectives to be achieved, the employees who can interact with each other, and the desire to contribute to the realization of the goals of the employees. The *efficacy* of

¹ Correspondence: email zdemirtas@firat.edu.tr

organizations depends on their degree of realization. Organizations also have to meet the individual needs of their employees. The level of meeting the needs of the employees indicates the *adequacy* of the organizations (Barnard, 1938, cited: Aydın, 1994: 14). It is expected that both the efficacy and the adequacy levels of the schools with basic input, function and product are high. The organizational values of schools and the affective commitment of employees are closely related to educational goals. Educational goals –to train knowledgeable, competent, worthy and conscious individuals- lead to how organizational values should be in schools. The acceptance and appeal of these goals by the managers and the teachers will have an impact on their organizational commitment. Job satisfaction and organizational silence behaviors of employees are related to adequacy of organization. As the adequacy levels of schools increase, it is expected that the level of job satisfaction of the employees increases and the behavior of organizational silence decreases. In terms of schools, managers and teachers are required to have strong organizational values, a high level of job satisfaction and organizational commitment. On the other hand, employees are not required to exhibit organizational silence. The silence of employees is undesirable because organizational silence refers to the avoidance behavior of employees expressing the problems they see in the organization or expressing their thoughts towards developing the organization.

For many years, values have been among the main research topics examined by many different disciplines (Sağnak, 2004; Dönmez & Cömert, 2007). While values affect the behavior of employees at individual level, they constitute organizational culture at the organizational level and guide organizational activities (Vurgun & Öztop, 2011). For this reason, employees' values can be examined as individual values and organizational values. Individual and organizational values are considered to be related and distinct from each other. Individual values develop in the social environment and are seen as products of the social system. In this context, they cannot be considered apart from social values (Uyguç, 2003). Values are important determinants of behavior and guide which criteria can be used to decide. The first step in understanding how both individual values and organizational values affect the decision-making process is to examine the interaction between these two perspectives (Liedtka, 1989). Organizational values are considered as criteria for determining and evaluating the qualifications of employees (Karaköse & Altinkurt, 2009). These values are shared by the members of the organization and determine what is good or bad (Demirtaş & Güneş, 2002: 123). Some organizational values created by organizations play an important role in many organizational activities such as identity, culture, individual-organizational harmony and socialization (Bourne & Jenkins, 2013). There is no value-free education. Values guide educators about what is right, what is wrong, and what is prioritized and important in teaching (Akbaba-Altun, 2003). Values are important or not important, not true or false (Thyssen, 2009: 220). Meglino and Ravlin (1998) argue that the values of individuals are the product of the cultural or social system they live in. An organization's values and working norms guide and act as organizational actions and employees as crucial components of the culture (Bowen & Schneider 1988, cited.: Kwon, Beatty & Lueg, 2000).

In a research on psychologists, it has been found that organizational values have a significant effect on job satisfaction (Burke, Oberklaid & Burgess, 2005). In another research conducted on teachers, it has been found that value based management is an important predictor of job satisfaction (Altinkurt & Yılmaz, 2012). Ostroff, Shin and Kinicki (2005) found a positive relationship between the values of bank employees and job satisfaction. Arslan (2006) found a strong relationship between job satisfaction and values in the research conducted by teachers. Based on the results of this research, it can be said that there is a relation between organizational values and job satisfaction and that organizational values are a predictive variable. There is a meaningful relationship between values and affective commitment. Strong values cause strong organizational commitment (Hüseyinliklioğlu, 2010; Finegan, 2000; Ostroff, Shin & Kinicki, 2005).

Contrary to the above two relations, organizational values and organizational silence are inversely related (Meydan, Köksal & Ugurlu-Kara, 2015; Sarıbay & Kayarlı, 2016). While organizational values are strengthening, organizational silence is weakening. The following hypothesis is based on the above literature:

H₁: Organizational values influence job satisfaction positively.

H₂: Organizational values influence affective commitment positively.

H₃: Organizational values influence organizational silence negatively.

Job satisfaction refers to a positive or pleasant emotional state resulting from someone's appreciation of their work or experience (Demirtaş, 2010). High job satisfaction is related to an employee love his/her work, colleagues, work environment. An employee with high job satisfaction emphasizes his positive qualities and technical aspects and identifies himself with the job. On the other hand, if a person develops negative attitudes towards work-related conditions and situations, job dissatisfaction arises. An employee who has negative emotions about his/her work falls into work stress. Some organizational factors affect job satisfaction; wages, job opportunities, labor turnover rate, working environment, duration of work, number of employees at work and relations between employees.

Reyes and Shin (1995) found that teachers' job satisfaction is a determinant of their commitment and must be present before organizational commitment (see Bogler, 2001). Through path analysis, Joharis (2016) has found that job satisfaction positively affects leadership, organizational culture, business motivation and organizational commitment of teachers. Culibrk, Delic, Mitrovic and Culibrk (2018) found that job satisfaction had a positive effect on organizational commitment. In this relationship, the work participation plays a partial mediator role. Lambert, Qureshi, Frank, Klahm and Smith (2018) found a linear, moderate and meaningful relationship between job satisfaction and affective commitment. In the study conducted by Tadampali and Hadi (2017), it was determined that organizational commitment plays an intermediary role in the effect of job satisfaction on performance. Hypothesis 4 has been developed in accordance with the above research.

H₄: Job satisfaction influence organizational commitment positively.

Pinder and Harlos (2001: 334) defined silence as *“the withholding of any form of genuine expression about the individual’s behavioral, cognitive and/or affective evaluations of his or her*

organizational circumstances to persons who are perceived to be capable of effecting change or redress." As seen in the definition, organizational silence is a factor that affects organizational development negatively and hinders organizational integration. Morrison and Milliken (2000: 707) view organizational silence as a potential obstacle to organizational change and development. Nevertheless, they highlight that silence reduces job satisfaction and job loyalty by reducing organizational commitment and trust. According to them, the dynamics that cause organizational silence are (p: 709): some features of upper management; organizational and environmental characteristics; implicit beliefs of managers; managers' fear of negative feedback; organizational structure and policies; administrative applications; factors affecting staff interaction; different demographic characteristics between intermediate and senior managers.

Employees can give some messages to their managers or organizations with their silent behavior (Yaman & Ruçlar, 2014: 37). These messages should be understood correctly. The reactions of the managers are the factors that determine the voice or silence of the employees. Individual evaluates the results in terms of voice or silence behavior. Indeed, no matter what level of equipment, knowledge and skill, individuals learn to talk actively and consciously or remain silent (Aktas & Simsek, 2015: 207).

Van Dyne, Ang and Botero (2003: 1360) argue that silence and voice can be seen as opposing poles, since voice implies important issues and problems in organizations, silence implies to remain silent. They (2003: 1362) made a three-dimensional classification of organizational silence: acquiescent silence, defensive silence, and prosocial silence. *Acquiescent silence* is withholding relevant ideas, information, or opinions, based on resignation. *Defensive silence* is withholding relevant ideas, information, or opinions as a form of self-protection, based on fear. *Prosocial silence* is withholding work-related ideas, information, or opinions with the goal of benefiting other people or the organization based on altruism or cooperative motives.

Yaman and Kuçlar (2014: 46) found a moderate and in reverse relationship between organizational silence and organizational culture. In other words, as the organizational culture weakens, the silent behaviors of employees increase. There is a negative and meaningful relationship between organizational silence and organizational commitment perceptions of employees. As the organizational silence increases, the organizational commitment of employees decreases (Bahadır & Certel, 2016, Deniz, Noyan & Ertosun 2013, Eroğlu, Adıgüzel & Öztüek, 2011, Kahveci, 2010, Morrison & Milliken 2000, Nikmaram, etc. 2012, Önder, 2017, Panahi et al., 2012, Salha, Cinnioğlu & Yenişehirlioğlu 2016). Hypothesis 5 was developed in accordance with the above literature.

H₅: Organizational silence influence organizational commitment negatively. Organizational commitment refers to the employee's psychological integration with the organization, the desire to embrace organizational goals and objectives, and the desire to continue to work in the organization (Gürbüz, 2006: 58). Employees adopt organizational goals through organizational commitment (Kurtulmuş, 2016: 288). Organizational commitment includes qualifications such as the desire of employees to stay in the organization, the quality of their relationship, their purpose, loyalty,

internalization of interests and efforts (Çoğaltan, 2015). Research on organizational commitment is usually based on a three-factor commitment model found by Meyer and Allen. The definitions of Meyer and Allen (1991: 67) are as follows:

“Affective commitment refers to the employee’s emotional attachment to, identification with, and involvement in the organization. Employees with a strong affective commitment continue employment with the organization because they want to do so. Continuance commitment refers to an awareness of the costs associated with leaving the organization. Employees whose primary link to the organization is based on continuance commitment remain because they need to do so. Finally, normative commitment reflects a feeling of obligation to continue employment. Employees with a high level of normative commitment feel that they ought to remain with the organization”(p, 67).

Affective commitment refers to identification with the organization and a sense of loyalty (Kurtulmuş, 2016: 289). This is like a heartfelt commitment to a person being linked to their goals and values (Cho, Eum & Lee, 2013: 518). Employees with a strong affective commitment continue to stay in the organization because they want to do so. Continuance commitment refers to the awareness of costs associated with departure from the organization. Employees who are based on continued commitment to the main connections remain in the organization because they have to do so. Normative commitment reflects the obligation to continue working. Employees with high levels of normative commitment are expected to remain in the organization. Because affective commitment dimension in terms of organizational commitment in literature is frequently used alone (Çınar & Yeşil, 2017: 288), this study is the affective commitment dimension which is meant by the concept of organizational commitment.

The antecedents of affective commitment are divided into four categories: personal characteristics, structural, job-related characteristics and work experience (Meyer and Allen, 1991: 69). When employees are highly committed to their organizations, employees, the organization and the society benefit from it. Thus, the commitment of teachers can be a bridge between the individual and the school. The high level of commitment of teachers to their schools means that they must devote themselves to devoting themselves to the school (Ting, 2010: 357).

2. The Importance of Research

The fact that managers and teachers have strong organizational values can lead to the formation and preservation of a strong organizational culture. A school with a strong culture enhances its effectiveness within the community. Strong organizational values accepted by the community form a strong bridge between school and society. The staffs working in organizations where strong cultures dominate, do their job well and get satisfaction from work. Organizational commitment, especially affective commitment, of personnel with high levels of job satisfaction increases. Strong organizational values, and therefore organizational culture, will cause organizational voice behaviors to

exhibit much more of the organizational silence behavior of the staff. In other words, strong organizational values will reduce organizational silence. Low organization silence will be effective in increasing the organizational commitment of staff.

Path analysis was performed in this study. Through the path analysis, it is tested whether the relations between variables that are theoretically revealed are strong and meaningful. In the analysis, the mutual interactions of multiple variables are examined from a holistic point of view and the relations between the variables are revealed (Karagöz, 2016: 1074). The research allows seeing the relations determined by many researches done in literature in a holistic view. As a result of the research, all the relationships between the organizational values, job satisfaction, organizational silences and organizational commitment of the administrators and teachers working at the schools can be seen in a single frame. This is the most original and important direction of the research. Because we have not witnessed a study that has gathered all these variables together. This theoretically generated model is shown in Figure 1. Research design is based on these patterns.

Figure 1: Conceptual model

According to our conceptual model, organizational values have positive effects on job satisfaction and affective commitment; organizational values have negative effect on organizational silence; job satisfaction has positive effect on affective commitment; organizational silence have negative affect on affective commitment. Apart from all these direct effects, indirect effects are also present.

3. Method

This research is a relational research model. The data were collected from the teachers working in the province of Elazığ (8500 persons) in the academic year of 2015-2016. A total of 900 scales were distributed and returned to 741 in 25 schools (2 kindergartens, 8 primary schools, 8 secondary schools and 5 high schools), which were thought to represent the population. Not fully marked 35 scales were excluded from the procedure. Statistical operations were performed on 706 scales processed in a computer

program and a YEM model was constructed. Missing data are incomplete and demographic characteristics are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics

Gender	n	%	Status / Task	n	%
Female	367	52.8	Manager	22	3.1
Male	338	47.9	Vice manager	47	6.7
			Teacher	635	89.9
Tenure	n	%	Age	n	%
0-5 years	63	8.90	20's	228	32.29
6-10 years	197	27.90	30's	268	37.96
11-15 years	192	27.20	40's	131	18.56
16-20 years	127	17.99	50's	37	5.56
21 and upper years	120	17.00	60's	7	0.99

Four scales were used in the study: (1) Management Scale According to Values, (2) Teaching Satisfaction Scale, (3) Organizational Silence Scale and (4) Affective Commitment Scale.

A. Management Scale According to Values: Applied Explicit Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) by Demirtaş and Ekmekyapar (2012), developed by Yılmaz (2006). The CFA goodness of fit measures were very high ($\chi^2 / df = 1.723$; GFI = .959; AGFI = .940; CFI = .983; NFI = .961; TLI = .979; RMSEA = .046 and SRMR = .035). The scale consists of two dimensions; individual values and organizational values. In this study, the dimensions of organizational values containing five items were used and excellent fit-good values were obtained ($\chi^2 / df = 2,242$; GFI = .996; AGFI = .980; CFI = .998; NFI = .996; TLI = .993; RMSEA = .043 and SRMR = .014).

B. Teaching Satisfaction Scale: The scale was developed by Ho and Au (2006). The adaptation of the scale to Turkish was done by Demirtaş (2015). He applied EFA and CFA to the scale and found goodness of fit measures quite high. The goodness of fit measures obtained in present research are very high too ($\chi^2/df = 1.033$; GFI = .998; AGFI = .9912; CFI = .1.00; NFI = .998; TLI = .1.00; RMSEA = .007; SRMR = .007).

C. Organizational Silence Scale: The original scale was developed by Kahveci and Demirtaş (2013). In this study, the CFA compliance values obtained are good ($\chi^2 / df = 1.88$; GFI = .963; AGFI = .934; CFI = .957; NFI = .914; TLI = .934; RMSEA = .060; SRMR = .045).

D. Affective Commitment Scale: Meyer and Allen's (1991) three-dimensional organizational commitment scale that includes eighteen items was adapted to Turkish by Wasti (2000). The Affective Commitment dimension that includes eight items was used in the present study. CFA was applied to the scale and three items (3, 6, and 8) were extracted from the SEM for acceptable goodness of fit measures. As a result, acceptable values were obtained ($\chi^2/df = .567$; GFI = .996; AGFI = .987; CFI = 1.00; NFI = .997; TLI = 1.00; RMSEA = .103; SRMR = .010).

E. Analyses: In interpreting the SEM values, the value ranges of Schermelleh-Engel et al. (2003) were used as criteria. The values are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Goodness of fit measures of the SEM

	χ^2 / df	GFI	AGFI	CFI	NFI	RMSEA	SRMR
Good Fit Values*	$0 \leq \chi^2 / df \leq 2$	$.95 \leq GFI \leq 1.00$	$.90 \leq AGFI \leq 1.00$	$.97 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$.95 \leq NFI \leq 1.00$	$0 \leq RMSEA \leq .05$	$0 \leq SRMR \leq .05$
Acceptable Fit Values*	$2 < \chi^2 / df \leq 3$	$.95 \leq GFI < .97$	$.85 \leq AGFI < .90$	$.95 \leq CFI < .97$	$.90 \leq NFI \leq .95$	$.05 < RMSEA \leq .08$	$.05 < SRMR \leq .10$

* Source: Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003, p:52

In order to construct the SEM model, the skewness and kurtosis values should be normal distribution. The skewness and kurtosis values between -1.0 and +1.0 indicate that the distribution is normal (Çokluk-Bökeoğlu et al., 2016: 16). The skewness and kurtosis values of the data were examined and found in the normal distribution range. The results of the analysis are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Skewness and kurtosis values

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Org. Values	706	3.186	.836	-.156	.092	-.058	.184
Job. Sat.	706	3.304	.905	-.159	.092	-.490	.184
Org. Silence	706	3.270	.637	-.186	.092	.082	.184
Affect. Com.	706	3.472	.825	-.150	.092	-.114	.184

After the normality test, a Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was established. Through the SEM, the direct and indirect effects of organizational values on job satisfaction, organizational silence and affective commitment have been determined. However, the direct and indirect effects of job satisfaction and organizational silence on affective commitment have been examined. A standard regression table derived from the SEM model was generated; so research hypotheses have been tested.

4. Results

Relationships between organizational values, job satisfaction, organizational silence and affective commitment were tested by SEM and the path diagram is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Structural modeling analyses

The goodness fit values of the SEM are good ($\chi^2/df = 2.526$, GFI = .934, AGFI = .917, CFI = .951, NFI = .922, RMSEA = .047, SRMR = .061). This finding indicates that the conceptual model is confirmed by SEM. When SEM is analyzed, the following results are obtained:

The first hypothesis of the research (*Organizational values influence job satisfaction positively*) was accepted. Organizational values have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at a low level ($r^2 = .29$). An increase of 1 percentage point in organizational values will result in an increase of .29 in job satisfaction. The effect force ($r^2 = .29$) obtained from the path scheme is lower than the isolated effect ($r^2 = .33$). When all the relationships in the model are considered together, the effect of organizational values on job satisfaction decreases.

The second hypothesis of the research was accepted (*Organizational values affect affective commitment positively*). Organizational values have a low level, positive and

significant effect on affective commitment ($r^2 = .25$). An increase of 1 percentage point in organizational values will result in an increase of .25 in affective commitment. The effect power ($r^2 = .25$) obtained from the path scheme is higher than the isolated effect ($r^2 = .19$). When all relationships in the model are considered together, the effect of organizational values on organizational commitment is rising. This rise is due to the mediating effect of job satisfaction and organizational silence.

The third hypothesis of the research was accepted (*Organizational values affect organizational silence negatively*). Organizational values have a low, negative and significant effect on organizational silence ($r^2 = -.20$). An increase of 1 percentage point in organizational values will cause a .20 decline in organizational silence. The efficiency of the path scheme ($r^2 = -.20$) is higher than that of the isolated effect ($r^2 = -.13$). When all the relations in the model are considered together, the effect of organizational values on organizational silence is rising.

The fourth hypothesis of the study was accepted (*Job satisfaction influence affective commitment positively*). Job satisfaction affects affective commitment moderately and positively. The effect of job satisfaction on affective commitment is moderate ($r^2 = .41$). An increase in job satisfaction by 1 percentage point will result in a .41 increase in affective commitment. The effect power ($r^2 = .41$) obtained from the path scheme is much higher than the isolated effect ($r^2 = .27$). This difference stems from the fact that job satisfaction moderates the effects of organizational values on organizational commitment.

The fourth hypothesis of the research was accepted (*Job satisfaction influence affective commitment positively*). Job satisfaction affects affective commitment moderately and positively. The effect of job satisfaction on affective commitment is moderate ($r^2 = .41$). An increase of 1 percentage point in job satisfaction will result in a .41 increase in affective commitment. The effect power ($r^2 = .41$) obtained from the path diagram is much higher than the isolated effect ($r^2 = .27$). When all the relationships in the model are considered together, the effect of job satisfaction on organizational commitment rises.

The fifth hypothesis of the research was accepted (*Organizational silence influence affective commitment negatively*). Organizational silence has a low and negative effect on affective commitment ($r^2 = -.12$). An increase of 1 percentage point in organizational silence will result in a .12 decrease in affective commitment. The effect power ($r^2 = -.12$) obtained from the path diagram is lower than the isolated effect ($r^2 = -.14$). When all the relationships in the model are considered together, the effect of organizational silence on organizational commitment is diminishing.

The standardized regression values obtained from the SEM show the estimation power of the variables. Standardized regression weights and significance values are taken from SEM and are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Regression weights and significance values of the model

Structural Relations		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p
Job Satisfaction	<--- Organizational Values	.331	.050	6.616	.000*
Affective Commitment	<--- Organizational Values	.187	.033	5.712	.000*
Organizational Silence	<--- Organizational Values	-.131	.033	-4.023	.000*
Affective Commitment	<--- Job Satisfaction	.273	.030	9.028	.000*
Affective Commitment	<--- Organizational Silence	-.140	.049	-2.868	.004*

* p<.01

According to Table 4 relations between all variables of the study are statistically significant at .01 level. Organizational values affect job satisfaction ($r^2 = .331$; $p = .000$) and affective commitment ($r^2 = .187$; $p = .000$) linearly, at a low level and significantly. Job satisfaction affects the affective commitment ($r^2 = .273$; $p = .000$) linearly, at a low level and significantly. However, organizational values have a negative, at a low level and significant effect on organizational silence ($r^2 = -.131$; $p = .000$). The finally organizational silence affects affective commitment ($r^2 = -.140$, $p = .004$) negatively, at a low level, and significantly.

Squared multiple correlations (R²) show that organizational values account for about 04% of total change in organizational silence, about 08% of total change in job satisfaction and 32.6% of total change in affective commitment.

Table 5: Standardized total impact values of the model

	Org. Values	Org. Silence	Job_Sat.	Affective_Commit.
Org. Silence	-.201	.000	.000	.000
Job_Sat.	.289	.000	.000	.000
Affective_Commit.	.392	-.122	.415	.000

According Table 5 the total impact power of organizational values on organizational silence is - .201. The total impact power of organizational values on job satisfaction is .289. The total impact power of organizational values on affective commitment is .392. In addition, the total impact power of organizational silence on affective commitment is - .122. The total impact power of job satisfaction on affective commitment is .415.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

Some values that may prevail in the school organization are: the implementation of rules in an impartial manner; successful completion of the initiated activities; to appreciate of teacher; a democratic workplace environment; the equal distribution of benefits and services. As these and similar values are strengthened, school culture will develop and strengthen. Strong school culture and strong values will increase the job satisfaction and affective commitment of both administrators and teachers. Although the SEM organizational values created directly affect affective commitment by 25

percent, the cumulative (both direct and indirect) influencing power appears to be about 40 percent.

Strong organizational values can give positive results by strengthening organizational commitment. For example: Employees can see organizational problems as their own problems, they can connect to the school more strongly, they can see themselves as part of the school. They might be proud to be a member of the school. The level of employees' adoption of school ownership and organizational goals may increase. Organizational commitment is one of the main activities of organizations to ensure their continuity. Individuals with organizational commitment are more harmonious, more sophisticated, more productive, work at a higher level of loyalty and responsibility, and cause fewer financials in the organization (Balcı, 2000). The overlap of individual goals and values with organizational goals and values strengthens organizational commitment. If this overlap occurs, the individual can participate at a high level in organizational activities and be connected with loyalty (Sezgin-Nartgün, 2006: 131).

Lawler states that the level of job satisfaction of teachers is of great importance in terms of increasing the quality of organizational life (cited by Şişman & Turan, 2004: 118). The results of this research reveal that organizational values play an important role in increasing the job satisfaction of school administrators and teachers. Job satisfaction causes an increase in affective commitment. The direct effect of job satisfaction on affective commitment is twenty-seven percent. But since job satisfaction plays a moderating role on affective commitment of organizational values, this effect is arise forty-one percent. The fact that school administrators display teachers' attitudes and behaviors that enhance job satisfaction can enhance the quality of organizational life. Teachers' affective commitment to the school can play an important role in school effectiveness.

Employees with strong organizational values do not hesitate in expressing the problems and negativity they see at work. The fact that the third hypothesis of the research (organizational values affect organizational silence negatively) has been accepted confirms this. Similarly, Ülker and Kanten (2009) found moderate linear relationships between organizational values and organizational commitment. It is possible to reach many research results confirming this relation (Deniz et al., 2013, Eroğlu et al., 2011, Kahveci, 2010, Morrison & Milliken, 2000, Nikmaram et al., 2012, Önder, 2017, Panahi et al., 2012, Tangirala & Ramanujam, 2008). On the other hand, while the direct negative impact of organizational silence on affective commitment is twelve percent, this negative effect increases to fourteen percent as organizational values play a moderating role on affective commitment. The high level of organizational silence of teachers will reduce affective commitment. Building strong organizational values and managing the school according to these values will reduce organizational silence and increase affective commitment.

References

1. Akbaba-Altun, S. (2003). Educational administration and values. *Değerler Eğitimi Dergisi / Journal of Values Education*, 1 (1), 7-18.
2. Aktaş, H. ve Şimşek, E. (2015). The role of perceptions of job satisfaction and emotional burnout in individuals' organizational silence attitudes. *International Journal of Management Economics and Business*, 11(24), 205-230.
3. Arslan, Z. (2006). *A research on religiosity, values and job satisfaction in teachers*. Unpublish Master Thesis, İstanbul: Marmara University Institute of Social Sciences.
4. Aydın, M. (1994). *Eğitim yönetimi / Educational Management*. Ankara: Hatipoğlu.
5. Balcı, A. (2000). *Örgütsel sosyalleşme kuram strateji ve taktikler / Organizational socialization theory strategy and tactics*. Ankara: Pegem A.
6. Bahadır, Z., & Certel, Z. (2016). Investigation of organizational silence and organizational commitment of physical education teachers. *Ahi Evran Üniversitesi Kırşehir Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 17(1), 135-146
7. Bogler, R. (2001). The influence of leadership style on teacher job satisfaction. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 37(5), 662-685.
8. Bourne, H. & Jenkins, M. (2013). Organizational values: a dynamic perspective. *Organization Studies*, 34(4), 495-514.
9. Burke, R. J., Oberklaid, F. & Burgess, Z. (2005). Organizational values, job experiences and satisfactions among female and male psychologists. *Community, Work and Family*, 8(1), 53-68.
10. Cho, D., Eum, W. S., & Lee, K.H. (2013). The impact of organizational learning capacity from the sociocognitive perspective on organizational commitment. *Asia Pacific Educ. Rev.*, 14, 511–522
11. Culibrk, J., Delic, M., Mitrovic, S. & Culibrk, D. (2018). Job satisfaction, organizational commitment and job involvement: the mediating role of job involvement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 1-12; doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00132.
12. Çınar, Ö, & Yeşil, S. (2016). A proposal of the structural equation model for review of the effect of organizational commitment and organizational support on employee performance. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Education Research*, 2(1), 286-301.
13. Çokluk-Bökeoğlu, Ö., Şekercioğlu, G., & Büyüköztürk, Ş. (2016). *Sosyal Bilimler İçin Çok Değişkenli İstatistik SPSS ve LISREL Uygulamaları / Multivariate Statistics for Social Sciences SPSS and LISREL Applications*. Ankara: Pegem A.
14. Çoğaltan, N. (2015). Organizational commitment of teachers: a meta-analysis study for the effect of gender and marital status in Turkey. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 15(4), 911-924
15. Demirtaş, H. & Güneş, H. (2002). *Eğitim yönetimi ve denetimi sözlüğü / Dictionary of educational management and supervision*. Ankara: Anı.
16. Demirtaş, Z. (2010). Teachers' Job Satisfaction Levels. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 9, 1069–1073.

17. Demirtaş, Z. (2015). The relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment: a study on elementary schools. *Kastamonu Education Journal*, 23(1), 253-268.
18. Demirtaş, Z., & Ekmekyapar, M. (2012). The effect values-based management practices of primary school principals on the school culture. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 18(4), 523-544.
19. Deniz, N., Noyan, A., & Ertosun, E.G. (2013). The relationship between employee silence and organizational commitment in a private healthcare company. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 99, 691-700.
20. Dönmez, B. & Cömert, M. (2007). Value systems of primary school teachers. *Değerler Eğitimi Dergisi / Journal of Values Education*, 5(14), 29-59.
21. Eroğlu, A.H., Adıgüzel, O., & Öztürk, U.C. (2011). Dilemma of silence vortex and commitment: Relationship between employee silence and organizational commitment. *SDU The Journal of Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 16(2), 97-124.
22. Finegan, J. E. (2000). The impact of person and organizational values on organizational commitment. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 73, 149-169
23. Gürbüz, S. (2006). A research on identifying the relationships between organizational citizenship behavior and affective commitment. *Ekonomik ve Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 3(1), 48-75.
24. Ho, C. L. & Au, W. T. (2006). Teaching Satisfaction Scale: Measuring Job Satisfaction of Teachers. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 66, 172-185.
25. Hüseyinklioğlu, B. (2010). *Bireysel değerler ve örgütsel bağlılık ilişkisi: Asker hastanesi çalışanları üzerinde bir araştırma*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation. Adana: Çukurova University Institute of Social Sciences.
26. Joharis, M. (2016). The effect of leadership, organizational culture, work motivation and job satisfaction on teacher organizational commitment at senior high school in Medan. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*. 5(10), 1-8.
27. Kahveci, G. (2010). *Relations between organizational silence and organizational commitment in primary schools*. Unpublished Master Thesis. Elazığ: Fırat University Institute of Social Sciences.
28. Kahveci, G. & Demirtaş, Z. (2013). School administrator and teachers' perceptions of organizational silence. *Education and Science*, 38 (167), 49-64.
29. Karagöz, Y. (2016). *SPSS ve AMOS Uygulamalı İstatistik Uygulamaları / SPSS and AMOS Applied Statistical Applications*. Ankara: Nobel.
30. Karaköse, T. & Altınkurt, Y. (2009). Opinions of school administrators and employees of provincial directorate of national education about management upon values (Sample of Kütahya). *Değerler Eğitimi Dergisi / Journal of Values Education*, 7(17), 49-67.

31. Kurtulmuş, M. (2016). The effect of diversity management on teachers' organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior. *Pegem Eğitim ve Öğretim Dergisi (PEGGOG)*, 6(3), 277-302.
32. Kwon, U., Beatty, S. E. & Lueg, J. E. (2000). Organizational values, work norms, and relational role behaviours: an empirical retail assessment. *International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 10(4), 401-416.
33. Lambert, E. G., Qureshi, H., Frank, J., Klahm, C. & Smith, B. (2018). Job stress, job involvement, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment and their associations with job burnout among indian police officers: a research note. *J Police Crim Psych*, 33, 85-99 ; doi: 10.1007/s11896-017-9236-y
34. Liedtka, J. M. (1989). Value Congruence: The interplay of individual and organizational value systems. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 8, 805-815.
35. Meglino, B. M. & Ravlin E.C. (1998). Individuals' values in organizations: concepts, controversies, and research. *Journal of Management*, 24(3): 351-389.
36. Meydan, H., Köksal, K., & Uğurlu-Kara, A. (2015). Silence in organization: the effect of organizational ethical values and the mediational role justice perception. *Gazi Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 17(2), 142-159.
37. Meyer, J. P. & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1, 61-89.
38. Morrison, E. W. & Milliken, F. J. (2000). Organizational silence: A barrier to change and development in a pluralistic world. *Academy of Management Review*, 25, 706-725.
39. Nikmaram, S., Yamchi, H. G., Shojaii, S., Zahrani, M.A., & Alvani, S. M. (2012). Study on relationship between organizational silence and commitment in Iran. *World Applied Sciences Journal* 17 (10): 1271-1277
40. Ostroff, C., Shin, Y., & Kinicki, A. J. (2005). Multiple perspectives of congruence: Relationships between value congruence and employee attitudes. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 26, 591-623
41. Önder, E. (2017). Organizational justice and organizational commitment as a predictor of organizational silence in secondary schools. *Ahi Evran Üniversitesi Kırşehir Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 18(2), 669-686.
42. Panahi, B., Veisheh, S.M., Divkhar, S., Kamari, F. (2012). An empirical analysis on influencing factors on organizational silence and its relationship with employee's organizational commitment. *Management Science Letters*, 2, 735-744.
43. Pinder, C. C. & Harols, P. (2001). Employee silence: Quiescence and acquiescence as responses to perceived injustice. *Research in Personnel and Human Resources Management*, 20, 331-369.
44. Sağnak, M. (2004). Value congruence and results in organizations. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi / Educational Administration in Theory & Practice*, 37, 72-95.
45. Salha, H., Cinnioğlu, Yazıt, H., & Yenişehirlioğlu, E. (2016). The effect of employees' organizational silence level on their organizational commitment: a

- research on the employees in the food and beverage businesses in Tekirdağ. *Balkan and Near Eastern Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(3), 5-15.
46. Sarıbay, B., & Kayalı, C.A. (2016). A research on the determination of relationship between employee silence and cultural values in public organisations in Izmir. *Ege Academic Review*, 3, 531-540.
47. Schermelleh-Engel, K., Moosbrugger, H., & Muler, H. (2003). Evaluating the fit of structural equation models: tests of significance and descriptive goodness-of-fit measures. *Methods of Psychological Research Online*, 8 (2), ss.23-74.
48. Sezgin-Nartgün, Ş. (2006). Teaching staff's views on organizational values (Abant İzzet Baysal University Faculty of Education example). *Değerler Eğitimi Dergisi / Journal of Values Education*, 4 (12), 129-148.
49. Şişman, M. & Turan, S. (2004). A study of correlation between job satisfaction and social-emotional loneness of educational administrators in Turkish public schools . *Osmangazi Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi* 5(1), 117-128.
50. Thyssen, O. (2009). *Bussines ethics and organizational values: a systems theoretical analysis*. Palgrave Macmillan.
51. Tadampali, A. C. T. & Hadi, A. (2017). The effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on work engagement and performance. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research (ASSEHR)*, 149, 55-56.
52. Ting, S. C. (2010). The effect of internal marketing on organizational commitment: Job involvement and job satisfaction as mediators. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 47(2), 353-382
53. Uyguç, N. (2003). Cinsiyet, bireysel değerler ve meslek seçimi / Gender, individual values and career choice. *D.E.Ü. İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi* 18(1), 93-103.
54. Ülker, F., & Kanten, P. (2009). A study on the relationship between silence climate, worker silence and organizational commitment in organizations. *Aksaray Üniversitesi İİBF Dergisi*, 1(2), 111-126.
55. Van Dyne, L., Ang, S., & Botero, I. C. (2003). Conceptualizing employee silence and employee voice as multidimensional constructs, *Journal of Management Studies*, 40(6), 1359-1392.
56. Vurgun, L. & Öztop, S. (2011). Significance of values for management and organizational culture. *S. D. Ü. İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi / S.D.U. The Journal of Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 16(3), 217-230.
57. Wasti, S. A. (2000). Örgütsel bağlılığı belirleyen evrensel ve kültürel etmenler: Türk kültürüne bir bakış / Universal and cultural factors affecting organizational commitment: a look at Turkish culture. *Türkiye'de Yönetim, Liderlik ve İnsan Kaynakları Uygulamaları*. ed. Z. Aycan. Ankara: *Türk Psikologlar Derneği*, 21: 201-224.
58. Yaman, E. & Ruçlar, K. (2014). Organizational Silence in Universities as the Predictor of Organizational Culture. *Yükseköğretim ve Bilim Dergisi/Journal of Higher Education and Science*, 4(1),36-50.

59. Yılmaz, K. (2006), *According to the managers and teachers of primary school, managing individual and organizational values in public primary schools and schools of school administrators according to these values*. Unpublished Doctoral Thesis. Ankara: Ankara University Institute of Educational Sciences.

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